

The Concept of Negation in Linguistics

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we tried to reveal the essence of negation in language and we determined its place in modern linguistics. A negative construction is a construction that expresses the absence of something, property, event or action in a sentence. This shows that the connection between the two views represented by the subject and the predicate does not actually exist. We also looked at its structure and the means of expressing negation in English. The negative can be used both with the predicate and with other parts of the sentence. The most common way to express negation in a sentence is to put the negation before the predicate. If the negation is in front of other parts of the sentence, then the placement of the accent and the construction of the sentence will be expressive.

Keywords: Negation, sentence construction, predicate, means of expressing negation, Negation construction, translation.

INTRODUCTION

The linguistic phenomenon of negation is generally recognized as one of the semantic universals, the initial semantic categories inherent in all languages of the world. Therefore, the cognitive meaning of negation, its role in the process of linguo-creative, interpretive activity of a linguistic personality deserves, firstly, serious consideration, and secondly, it is obvious that the universality of this phenomenon should reflect the basic laws of speech production [1].

Consideration of the functions and essence of negation is traditionally considered as an expression of the criterion of truth / falsity of the statement. The speaker evaluates the situation expressed by the corresponding positive statement as false, i.e. having no place in reality. So, for the sentence "he did not come" the opposite positive combination "he came" is assigned the value of falsity. Thus, "he did not come" in my opinion, is not true."

However, the explanation of the phenomenon of negation solely through the parameter "falsity/truth of the statement" is not exhaustive. In this case, we get the following chain of mental operations when constructing a negative statement: highlighting propositions and elements of subjective modality in a situation - constructing an affirmative statement - comparing this option with the objective state of affairs - setting, in case of discrepancy, negation, which in this case means "that, what I originally assumed is wrong." From this logical chain, the conclusion necessarily follows that a person, using negative sentences, demonstrates the fruit of his speech-thinking, but, however, corrected error. This assumption seems to be more than debatable, since it implies an unacceptably large number of errors and miscalculations in the process of speech generation regarding the criterion of truth / falsity of the situation - as one possibility, or as a second possibility - the conscious initial construction of a false positive statement solely in order to later declare it false.

Within the framework of logic, the expression "he did not come" rightly means "that he came is a lie." However, grammatical meanings, despite their inherent generalized nature, represent, first of all, a subjective speech element of semantics⁴. Within the framework of natural language, the necessary consequence of the first, negative, statement from the second, positive, seems doubtful. The

need for the initial construction of a positive statement would significantly complicate and slow down the speech-thinking process.

DISCUSSIONS

In addition, the interpretation of negation as "stating some kind of inconsistency" does not apply to assessing the truth or falsity of a negative statement in natural language. As V.V. Gurevich, "any of our statements are "stuffed" with references to the speaking subject". The statement "he did not come" is true, because it reflects the real state of affairs from the point of view of the speaker, includes the component "the speaker considers it true that ..." [5]. In our opinion, any statement for the speaker is the truth by definition, i.e. it is the result of a person's interpretive cognitive activity aimed at understanding the world (even in the case of a deliberate lie, the speaker seeks to present it to listeners as an absolute truth). Thus, both positive and negative statements describe the true, according to the speaker, state of affairs in the real world.

The loading of negative statements with an additional parameter - the obligatory comparison of them with the corresponding positive statements in order to recognize the falsity of the latter - would mean the asymmetry of speech generation in this aspect, since the linguistic literature does not state that when constructing a positive statement, it is necessary to compare it with the corresponding negative one in order to decide which one is true.

Negation must be understood as a special case of affirmation (in the broadest sense of the word). For example, the meaning of the negative proposition "he did not come" is to say that he did not come.

The logical concepts of affirmation and negation reflect, respectively, the presence or absence of an object, feature or phenomenon. It is the absence of an

object, feature or phenomenon that is stated using various means of expressing negation.

Negation in language should be defined as a statement of the absence of an object, attribute, phenomenon, expressed by linguistic means.

A statement in language is a statement of the presence of an object, attribute, phenomenon, expressed by linguistic means. Negation is a marked member of the opposition - Affirmation - Negation.

As Bakharev says, affirmation and negation are the most important signs of judgment. One of the most significant differences between logic and grammar is that the logical category of negation is characteristic only of judgments, while grammatical negation is characteristic of all types of sentences (declarative, interrogative, incentive). The second essential feature of grammatical sentences of various types is manifested in the fact that in them the meaning of negation often interacts with modality [4].

Logical negation interacts with linguistic negation at the level of concept - word. So, in the lexical system of the language there are contradictory and opposite antonyms, and in formal logic, positive and negative concepts are distinguished, between which there can be relations of contradiction (contradiction) or contrariety (opposite).

At the same time, there is no identity between logical negation and the word-formation structure of the word, since different word-formative means and their combinations are used to express negation; negative prefixes interact with other parts of the word and take an active part in the formation of its new lexical meaning. The negation expressed in a word with the help of a prefix can have a different degree of its expression. This is due to the linguistic correlation of the word with other words of the language, the presence of a semantic field (thematic

series of words), the wide word-formation possibilities of each word, the features of its functioning and use.

Negative judgments reflect a certain side of objective reality - the disunity that takes place in reality. Negation can have a different gradation, therefore, in negative sentences, various degrees of negation can be expressed, from weakened, barely noticeable to categorical.

Negative sentences of certain types in different languages have a logical basis. At the same time, grammatical negation, which is ultimately based on logical negation, is by no means always identical to the latter. The meaning of negation is intertwined with modal meanings, interacts with the grammatical meanings of aspect, mood, case, etc.

Negation is closely related to logical stress and actual division of the sentence. Usually the core of the statement (rheme) in a negative sentence contains a means of expressing negation. Negation occupies a special position among grammatical categories. It is characterized by universality, antiquity of origin, markedness, and the ultimate abstractness of meaning. Due to these features, negation is most closely associated with general grammatical categories, for example, predicativity.

From the moment that the process of dividing people into groups using different languages (due to geographical, historical and cultural prerequisites) began to occur in the history of civilization, the problem of decoding speech for communication has appeared. And since different nations have entered and are entering into trade, military, political, economic, cultural, scientific relations with each other throughout the history of mankind, then, undoubtedly, translation is one of the oldest types of rational human activity. And since ancient times, translation has been performing the function of interlingual and intercultural communication

of people, both between states and on the territory of multinational states. Examples are Ancient Carthage, Ancient Egypt, the states of Ancient Greece, the Roman Empire, the states of Central Asia, India, Iran, which included multilingual tribes and nationalities. The more multinational the state was, the more honorable place in it was occupied by translators. So, in ancient Carthage, the caste of translators enjoyed honor and respect, and their emblem was a bright and elegant parrot, the multi-colored plumage of which indicated which languages the translator was working with.

One of the important milestones in the development of translation was the emergence of writing. Firstly, it gave a powerful impetus to the intercultural exchange of values and achievements in various fields of human activity, and secondly, a new type of translation practice was formed, namely, written translation, which has been functioning since that moment along with interpretation. Not only oral statements, but also written texts began to be translated.

The human tendency to generalize what is happening in the world, the accumulation of vast experience in the course of translation practice, prompted translators to synthesize existing knowledge and create a theory of translation.

The modern theory of translation as a scientific direction arose in the middle of the 20th century. The impetus for its emergence and development was the sharp expansion of translation practice to meet urgent needs. A boom of comparative, contrastive research is beginning, carried out by the method of translation and for translation, which in essence represent particular translation theories for specific pairs of languages. Theoretical research leads to the formation of the conceptual apparatus of the theory of translation, the development of the main issues of the theory of translation.

The central concept of the theory of translation is the very concept of "translation". The content of this concept has changed over the centuries and today is interpreted ambiguously. First of all, it should be borne in mind that the concept of "translation" is ambiguous. Firstly, this concept denotes translation as a kind of intellectual activity, that is, a process. Secondly, translation as a result of this process is a product of translation activity, in other words, a speech work (translated text) created by a translator.

Serving as a means of communication between people of different nationalities, translation is a means of interlingual and intercultural communication. According to A.D. Schweitzer, "translation can be defined as a unidirectional and two-phase process of interlingual and intercultural communication, in which, on the basis of a primary text subjected to a purposeful ("translation") analysis, a secondary text (metatext) is created that replaces the primary text in a different linguistic and cultural environment. ... A process characterized by an attitude towards conveying the communicative effect of the primary text, modified in part by the differences between two languages, two cultures and two communicative situations.

One of the fundamental points when considering translation is the understanding that communication is the interaction of individuals, in which communicants appear as subjects of culture, representatives of a certain linguo-socio-cultural community. And translation, as a type of mediation, is not only a means of interlingual, but also a means of intercultural communication. The consideration of translation as intercultural communication follows from the understanding of language as a component of culture, as a single socio-cultural formation, and culture as a set of material and spiritual achievements of society, including the whole versatility of the historical, social and psychological

characteristics of an ethnic group, its traditions, views, values, institutions, behavior, way of life, living conditions - in a word, all aspects of his being and consciousness, including language. With this understanding, the language is interpreted as a single socio-cultural formation, reflecting the characteristics of an ethnic group as a carrier of a certain culture, distinguishing it from other cultures.

According to the nature of the attitude towards reality expressed in the sentence, they are divided into affirmative and negative. Denial is often accompanied by affirmation, both potential and expressed. Sentences that include grammatically formed negation and affirmation are called negative-affirmative. Such sentences can be either simple or complex. With an asyndetic connection of parts of a complex sentence, the combination of affirmation / negation can be one of the means of communication that also serves to express the meaning of the comparison.

Two negative particles sometimes form an affirmative sentence (a sentence with a double negation), since the negation of the negation occurs in it. Negation in English as a way to reduce the significance of an utterance is found mainly in three types of constructions: direct, hidden and double.

1. Direct negation, as a rule, refers to the verb or transferred to the verb of thinking (transferred negation), or is expressed in words of indefinite meaning (non-assertive words). A construction with direct negation can replace the emotionally colored word of the construction with an affirmative one; in such cases, a more neutral synonym is chosen, and the meaning of the implied (understatement) is derived from the context, since it cannot be unambiguously determined by replacing it with a synonymous turnover or by mechanical substitution of a word with the opposite meaning.

For example: He is not amused.

This sentence can be interpreted as I'm bored /displeased/tired, etc. He can't help watching TV for hours.

This sentence can be expressed in the words he is a TV addict.

We are not on friendly / speaking terms with them.

And this sentence can be said as We are enemies.

Negative constructions often rely on the use of adverbs of degree like very, too, particularly, quite and words of indefinite meaning like anything, anywhere, etc., which reduce the negative effect.

For example: He is not particularly fond of snakes.

(I'm not fond of snakes = I'm afraid of snakes.) He is not too happy about it.

(She is not happy... = She is unhappy / miserable.)

Also, negation can be transferred to the verb of thinking: I don't suppose it's right, (cf.: I suppose it's not right. = It is all wrong.)

Such phrases are indispensable when expressing a negative attitude, complaints, explanations, apologies, etc., for example, so that, say, during an important meeting or at an exam, not to lose face, simply saying: I don't understand, you can successfully use the understatement: Sorry, but I'm not quite clear on... or express your disagreement using formulas like I'm not sure I quite could agree / I don't quite see it the same way / I don't think it's quite that simple.

2. Hidden negation takes place in affirmative sentences with negative or minimizing adverbs or the corresponding verbs and participles.

Latent negation can be expressed implicitly in affirmative sentences by replacing the direct negation, for instance, with negative adverbs like hardly, barely, scarcely, minimizing adverbs few, little, or appropriate verbs and participles like fail, lack, etc.

For example: Not barely touched his drink.

(He didn't touch his drink, He drank nothing.) His contribution could hardly be underestimated.

(His contribution could not be underestimated. = It is highly praised.) The author failed to mention these facts.

(The author did not mention these facts.)

3. Double negation occurs when words of a negative meaning are used in a negative sentence. Negation as a method of underestimation (mitigation) is usually used when it is necessary to weaken the emotional impact of stylistically colored words expressing a critical attitude, disagreement, hostility, etc. When words of a negative meaning, for example, with negative prefixes or prepositions, are used in a negative sentence, there is, as it were, a double negation.¹

For example:

Our new director doesn't look unfriendly, he is not likely to be devoid of human weaknesses. (He looks friendly and human.)

CONCLUSION

In the process of work, we found out that negation in English is expressed using:

1. negative particles not and by;
2. negative pronouns;
3. negative adverbs;
4. negative conjunctions and prepositions;
5. negative affixes and derivational morphemes;

In addition, negation is expressed with the help of intonation, stress, subjunctive mood and words with negative semantics. We studied negation in the functional-semantic and functional-pragmatic organization of the field and

identified a trend of stability in the regularity of the use of the means of negation in the language indicated above.

Moreover, we determined that there are three types of negative constructions: 1. expressing direct negation; 2. concluding a hidden negation; 3. carrying a double negation. Each of the above types of negative constructions has its own characteristics and difficulties in translating.

References:

1. Vinogradov B.C. Introduction to translation studies. - M.: Publishing house of the Institute of General Secondary Education of the Russian Academy of Education, 2001. - P.105.
2. Searle J. Classification of speech acts. - M.: Higher School, 2001. - P.31.
3. Terminosova S.G. Language and international communication. Proc. allowance. – M.: Valent, 2000. – P.112.
4. Searle J. Classification of speech acts. - M.: Higher School, 2001. - P.31.